

COMPUTER-AIDED THERMOFORMING OF FRTP WITH DIGITAL IMAGE-BASED MEASUREMENT OF LARGE STRAIN DISTRIBUTION

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SUMMARY: The thermoforming techniques for fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites (FRTP) such as vacuum forming, deep-draw forming and press forming are of great interest recently aiming at the manufacturing of low-cost components. This paper proposes a novel digital engineering technology in thermoforming of FRTP. The textiles are supposed to be suited as the reinforcement due to their deformability because the large deformation occurs. In other words, however, the microscopic architecture changes largely, which is very much influential on the macroscopic properties of FRTP components. Hence, the measurement of large deformation in thermoforming is important to design FRTP components so that their functions meet the requirement. In pursuit of this, a novel digital image-based strain measurement technique is proposed, and is applied to the deep-drawing of aramid rib-knit/PP composites. With this technique, a computer-aided thermoforming system is described that integrates 3D-CAD, rapid tooling and FEA (finite element analysis).

KEYWORDS: fiber reinforced thermoplastics (FRTP), thermoforming, textile, large strain, digital engineering

INTRODUCTION

The low-cost manufacturing and the recycling have been the critical issues for polymer matrix composites. The thermoforming techniques such as vacuum forming, deep-draw forming and press forming of continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastics (FRTP) are supposed to meet those requirements, and have been studied extensively [1-6]. For the low-cost development and manufacturing of FRTP, the efficiency in design, low-cost mold die and short forming time are essential. They are achieved by introducing the digital engineering technology using 3D-CAD,

rapid prototyping and/or rapid tooling and finite element analysis (FEA). For instance, new commercial software to simulate the thermoforming process has been put to use quite recently [7]. Recent rapid tooling techniques include metal tooling that is directly used as mold die [8].

One important point in the thermoforming of FRTP with continuous fiber reinforcement is that the large deformation occurs as shown in Fig.1. This requires the deformable and flexible reinforcement such as the textiles including woven fabrics and knitted fabrics. The large deformation of the reinforcement results in the change of the microscopic architecture and also the change of the macroscopic properties, which are hardly predictable in the initial design stage. The design of FRTP component should be based on the largely deformed reinforcement to meet the required macroscopic functions. The process simulation as mentioned above can be one solution to this problem, but the current existing software cannot consider the micro-structural phenomena and cannot link with the response analysis of the component. Only the microstructure-based simulation by, for instance, the homogenization method might be able to construct the consistent system [9,10], but its application is limited at this moment.

Fig. 1 Large deformation during vacuum forming. ((b) aluminum die, (c) top view)

Instead of the process simulation, a novel digital image-based measurement technique of large strain distribution in the thermoformed components is proposed in this paper.

DIGITAL ENGINEERING IN THERMOFORMING OF FRTP

To achieve the efficiency in design and low-cost tooling, 3D-CAD should be the core in the future digital engineering system. Also the finite element analysis (FEA) of the component in usage is essential for the design of component to meet the required functions and properties. To consider the effect of largely deformed reinforcement on the macroscopic properties in FEA, a novel digital image-based measurement technique is proposed. Once the large strain distribution including all strain components (normal and shear strains), the homogenization method [11], for instance, can predict the properties necessary for FEA. Fig.2 shows the schematic flow of the proposed computer-aided thermoforming system.

Fig. 2 Computer-aided thermoforming system with digital image-based strain measurement technique

The developed digital image-based measurement technique consists of the following three steps; image capturing, digitization and calculation of strain distribution. The reason why the image-based technique is needed is that no other methods can recognize the local portion of the complicated shaped components as shown in Fig.3.

Fig. 3 Demonstrative application of image-based technique to complicated shaped component

DIGITAL IMAGE-BASED STRAIN MEASUREMENT TECHNIQUE

As mentioned above, the proposed technique consists of the following three steps; image capturing, digitization and calculation of strain distribution.

In the image capturing step, no special camera system such as the stereo mapping is needed and the home camera is enough usable. Moreover, by linking with 3D-CAD, fewer images are needed than other existing systems [12]. This also enables us to treat the complicated shaped component with free surface as shown in Fig.1. The STL data format in CAD that represents the surface data is utilized. Fig.4 shows the STL data of the component in Fig.1.

Fig. 4 STL expression of component with free surface

Fig. 5 Digitization by images and STL data

Fig.5 shows the schematic of the digitization step using the captured images and STL data. In this research, the regular grid to express the component (surface) instead of discrete points [12], because the discrete points cannot determine the large deformation uniquely and also because only the local portion cannot be measured by the discrete points as shown in Fig.6.

Fig. 6 Use of grid instead of discrete points

Using the grid, basically, the deformation gradient tensor \mathbf{F} can be defined by the gravity point and the grid point based on the continuum mechanics. However, the orthogonal coordinate system results in the inclined system after forming even if the course-wale axes are referred for textile composites. No information on the rotational motion of the coordinate system is obtained during multi-step forming process. To solve this problem, the polar decomposition of the deformation gradient tensor is utilized as in the next equation [13].

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{U} \quad (1)$$

\mathbf{R} denotes the rotational motion and \mathbf{U} denotes the right stretch tensor. In this study, the Biot's strain \mathbf{B} is employed that is calculated by only \mathbf{U} .

$$\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{U} - \mathbf{I} \quad (2)$$

The Biot's strain is intuitively useful rather than, for instance, the Green-Lagrange strain that is used in the so-called GSA (Grid Strain Analysis) [6, 14] as shown in Fig.7.

Fig.7 Comparison between Biot's strain and other strain definition

Fig. 8 Projection of grid points onto tangential plane

Then, once the grid points are projected onto the tangential plane as shown in Fig.8, the two-dimensional orthogonal coordinate system is arbitrary. Finally, the deformation gradient tensor \mathbf{F} can be calculated as shown in Fig.9 [13].

Fig. 9 Schematic of calculating deformation gradient tensor

APPLICATION TO DEEP-DRAWING OF KNITTED FABRIC COMPOSITE

The proposed digital image-based strain measurement technique has been applied to the deep-drawn cup shaped FRTP component. Aramid rib-knit fabric/PP composite is used. Fig.10(a) shows the microscopic rib-knit structure used in this study, and Fig.10(b) shows the captured images of the deep-drawn component. Referring the dimension of the unit microstructure of the rib-knit fabric, the grid size is set to be 3mm. As shown in Fig.9, the strain is calculated with the resolution of 1.5mm in this case. The diameter is 59mm, and the height of the component in Fig.10(b) is 51.6mm. Fig.11 shows the digitized component by three images in Fig.10(b) and STL data. Fig.11 agrees well with Fig.10(b).

(a) rib-knit structure

(b) deep-drawn component

Fig. 10 Deep-drawn component of aramid rib-knit fabric/PP composite

Fig.11 Digitized component

Fig.12 Measured Biot's strain

Fig. 13 Schematic of micro-scale large deformation of rib-knit structure

Fig.12 shows the measured Biot's strains, B11 (normal strain in course direction), B22 (normal strain in wale direction) and B12 (shear strain). Larger strain is observed in course direction than wale direction, which is due to the anisotropy of rib-knit structure. Locally very large strain more than 200% is observed. Also, the microscopic behavior of the rib-knit structure is captured locally by using the small grid as shown in Fig.13, which is supposed to be due to the initial inhomogeneity.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, a computer-aided thermoforming system of FRTP is described using a digital image-based large strain measurement technique. Biot's strain is used to express the large strain up to 200%. 3D CAD is used in STL data format for the digitization of images. This leads to the measurement of complicated shaped component with free surface. Compared with other existing system, less images are needed and local evaluation is capable. A demonstrative application to deep-drawn component of aramid rib-knit/PP composite is shown.

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